

UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

Collocation and colligation analysis of "vaccine"

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INTRODUCTION

During the COVID-19 pandemic, major countries have launched a vaccine for their own population and allies. It is interesting to see how a word 'vaccine' within a corpus made from the keywords of major vaccine brands could reveal some sense of political schism.

OBJECTIVE

To categorize collocates, semantic preference, semantic prosody, and variation of "vaccine".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Corpus built from: **Sketch Engine**

Keywords: **Pfizer, Moderna, Sinovax, and Novavax**

Regular expression: **[vaccine].[n*]**

Corpus analysis programme: **AntConc**.

Collocation analysis parameter: **-3 +3 adjacent words**

Colligation analysis: **KWIC display, N+1 and N+2**

RELATED LITERATURE

Sinclair, John. 2004[1996]. The search for units of meaning. *Textus* 9(1). 75-106. Reprinted in *Trust the text: Language, corpus and discourse*, 24-48. London: Routledge.

RESULTS

Collocation Analysis

- The most frequent collocate is "**nationalism**" (8 hits) as in *vaccine nationalism*.
- The second most frequent is "**viability**" (4 hits) as in *vaccine viability*.
- The third most frequent collocate is "**validate**" (4 hits) which co-occurs specifically with Sinovac as in *WHO validates Sinovac COVID-19 vaccine*.

Rank	Freq	Freq(L)	Freq(R)	Stat	Collocate
1	10	2	8	6.29393	nationalism
2	5	1	4	6.14192	viability
3	4	4	0	6.14192	validates
4	3	3	0	6.14192	treffis
5	3	2	1	6.14192	shingrix
6	3	3	0	6.14192	rushes
7	3	3	0	6.14192	ptau
8	5	0	5	6.14192	psv
9	3	3	0	6.14192	parainfluenza
10	3	0	3	6.14192	morena
11	5	1	4	6.14192	lobby
12	3	3	0	6.14192	licensee

Colligation Analysis

- **N+1**
 - construction **may be, can be, could be, will be**
- **N+2**
 - construction **is + V.participle**: is authorized, is given, is approved, is expected
 - construction **is + adjective**: is safe, is available, is effective, is similar

FULL PAPER

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KWIC N+1 Overview

Semantic Preference

- In the **N+1** level, we found **modal verbs** and **will** that indicate different levels of probability or possibility.
- In the **N+2** level, we saw **passive voice construction** indicating an emphasis on vaccine and **descriptive construction** of vaccine giving more details about or modifying vaccine.

Semantic Prosody

- Language users see vaccine as **an object**. At N+1 level, vaccine is associated with uncertainty and possibility, and at N+2, vaccine was described and explained what has been done to it.

CONCLUSION

With the 4 keywords of leading vaccine brands from the east and the west, it is not surprised that the most frequently cooccurring word is **nationalism**. In addition, vaccine has been **perceived as an object** and linked with **uncertainty and possibility**.